

A Study of Rene Descartes' "Rationalism"

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Abstract

This paper will discuss the rationalism of Rene Descartes is an attempt to solve the problem "Why does Rene Descartes accept the concept of reason in his philosophical system?" (Research Problem) The answer to this question will be provided by showing that Descartes' was one of the famous rationalists who hold reason as the only valid source to attain certain knowledge. (Tentative Solution) The research methods which will be used are descriptive method and evaluative method. (Research Methods) This paper will contribute to realization than man is rational begin, so reason is important role in human life. (Contribution)

Key Words: Reason, Rationalist, Knowledge.

Introduction

In Contemporary western Philosophy the development is known as Rationalism. When the authority of the Christian church was finally loosened many people came to believe that knowledge of the world could be gained by the use of reason alone.

Rationalists accepted reason is the unique path to knowledge it was launched by Descartes after whom the outstanding figures were Spinoza and Leibniz.

Descartes, Spinoza and Leibniz were among the most gifted of all mathematicians. They believed that if only the methods of mathematics were applied to human attempts to understand the world, the world could be fully explained.

The first modern Philosopher, Rene' Descartes believed science and mathematics could explain and predict events in the physical world.

Descartes developed the Cartesian coordinate system for graphing equations and geometric shapes. Modern maps use a grid system that can be traced back to Cartesian graphing techniques.

Descartes wished to find a method as certain as mathematics to understand the world itself. Mathematical demonstrations begin from a minimal number of premises of utmost simplicity that were undoubtedly true.

So Descartes searched for indubitable premises. He began by doubting everything possible and they came to the famous conclusion of "Cogito Ergo Sum" meaning that he could not doubt that he doubted. (I think, therefore I am).

The famous Rationalists are Rene Descartes, Benedict de Spinoza and Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz.

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Chapter I

Rationalism in Modern Philosophy

1. 1. The Meaning of Rationalism

Rationalism is “any view appealing to reason as a source of knowledge or justification.” In more technical term, it is a method or a theory in which the criterion of the truth is not sensory but intellectual and deductive. Different degrees of emphasis on this method or theory lead to a range of rationalist standpoints, from the moderate position “that reason has precedence over other ways of acquiring knowledge” to the more extreme position that reason is “the unique path to knowledge.”

Rationalism is both a method and a theory of truth. It is an important philosophical theory in the seventeenth century. Rationalism is often contrasted with empiricism.

Rationalism is a development of the enlightenment that emphasizes a “politics of reason” center upon support of the concepts of rational choice, utilitarianism, secularism, and irreligion; this has especially been promoted by liberalism.

Rationalism is often contrasted with empiricism. The empiricist’s view holds that all ideas come to us through experience, either through the external senses or through such inner sensations as pain and gratification, and thus that knowledge is essentially based on or derived from experience.

Proponents of some varieties of rationalism argue that, starting with foundational basic principles, like the axioms of geometry, one could deductively derive the rest of all possible knowledge. The philosophers who held this view most clearly were Spinoza and Gottfried Leibniz, whose attempts to grapple with the epistemological and metaphysical problem raised by Descartes led to a development of the fundamental approach of rationalism.

Moreover rationalism is predicting and explaining behavior based on logic. The distinction between rationalists and empiricists was drawn at a latter period, and would not have been recognized by the philosopher involved. Also, the distinction was not as clear-cut as is sometimes suggested; for example, Descartes and Locke have similar views about the nature of human ideas. The three main rationalists were all committed to the importance of empirical science, and in many respects the empiricists were closer to Descartes in their methods and metaphysical theories than were Spinoza and Leibniz.

Since the enlightenment, rationalism is usually associated with the introduction of mathematical methods into philosophy, as in Descartes, Leibniz, and Spinoza.

Chapter II

Philosophy of Rene Descartes

Descartes was a mathematician as well as a philosopher and he is broadly regarded as the founder of modern western philosophy. His ambition was to begin philosophy a new, establishing it on grounds certain enough to support an edifice of indubitable knowledge.

Rene' Descartes was born in a village near Tours in France in 1596. At the age of eight years he entered the Jesuit College La Fleche in Anjou, where he would study classics, logic, and Aristotelian philosophy, as well as mathematics from the book of Clevis.

Descartes went on to obtain a degree in law from Poitier, then enlisted in the Dutch military. Military service was tradition in his family, and when the Thirty Years' War began he was encouraged to volunteer under in the Bavarian army. In his leisure time he studied mathematics having been influenced by the Dutch mathematician and scientist Beckman. Descartes dates his first new philosophical ideas and his analytical geometry from three dreams that he had while campaigning on the Danube. He saw November 19, 1619, the date of these dreams, as a landmark moment in his life. It was around 1619 that he may have started *Rules for the Direction of Mind*, his first major philosophical treaties, which would remain unfinished. This work discusses the proper method for engaging with science and rational theology.

Descartes traveled through Europe, moving from Bohemia, to Hungary, Germany, Holland and France from 1620 to 1628. In 1623 he is Paris where he met Messene, who would keep him in contact with his contemporaries in science. After Paris, he spent time in Venice, he returned to France in 1625. In 1629 Descartes moved to Holland where he would live in seclusion for 20 years. Occasionally during this time he would visit France, and he changed his address frequently to maintain his privacy.

During his first four year in seclusion he wrote *le Monde*, a thesis on physics defending a heliocentric view of the universe. 1633 was the year that Galileo's *Dialogue* was condemned by the Catholic Church, and although Descartes book was ready, he put off its publication out of concern that his views might too be censured. The incomplete manuscript of *Le Monde* was finally published in 1644. In 1637 Descartes published *Optics, Meteorology, and Geometry*, a collection of essays. The preface to the collection is titled *Discourse on the Method of Rightly Conducting the Reason and Seeking Truth in the Sciences*, and was written for the most part before 1633. A conclusion to the preface, added later, explained that he would publish despite of the risks because he needed readers to help confirm his scientific theories. In *Discourse* Descartes insists on the use of deductive reasoning, countering Francis Bacon's induction as introduced in *Novum Organum* from 1620. The work from these years forms the basis of some of Descartes most important contributions to mathematics and physics, including the introduction of what is now known as analytic geometry.

Descartes expanded on the metaphysical themes from his collection of essays in his *Meditations on the First Philosophy* in 1640. The Existence of God and the Distinction between Mind and Body are Demonstrated in this book. The six Meditations of the book are titled: Of the Things that we may doubt; Of the Nature of the Human Mind; of God: that he exists; of Truth and Error; of the essence of material Things; of the Existence of Material Things; and Of the Real Distinction between the Mind and the Body of Man. In *Meditations* Descartes argues that the mind and body are distinct substances, He writes that humans are spirits, and that their essential attributes are exclusively of the spirit (for example thinking, willing, and conceiving). The human spirit occupies a mechanical body, made up of extended substance. Attributes like sense perception, movement and appetite are of the body and not the spirit, so they do not comprise human essence. *Meditations* was published in Latin 1641, and translated into French in 1642.

Descartes' *Principia Philosophies* was published in 1644. Its four sections, titled *The Principles of Human Knowledge*, *The Principles of Material Things*, *Of the Visible World and The Earth*, are a study of mechanics, developing a mathematical foundation of the universe. The book concentrates on physical science, specifically the laws of motion and theory of vortices. In 1647 the French court granted Descartes a pension to honor his work.

Perhaps Descartes' most well-known philosophical ideas are his method of hyperbolic doubt, and the idea that through one may doubt, one may not doubt that one exists. The method of hyperbolic doubt is the refusal to accept either the authority of previous philosophers or information gleaned from one's own senses. He decided that in developing a foundation for philosophy anything that might be doubted must be rejected. Only what is beyond doubt is acceptable and may lead to truth. He finds that all that remains is the fact of doubting itself, and that something must exist to doubt, namely the philosopher himself.

Descartes always refused the Aristotelian and Scholastic traditions that had been the dominant shape of philosophy throughout the Medieval times, and he rejected religious influence in his scientific and philosophical studies. Throughout his life and afterwards his work was condemned by the Catholic Church, and was officially prohibited in 1663. Descartes was a devout Catholic influenced by the Reformation's challenge of Church authority, and he often uses a vocabulary influenced by scholastic thought. As long as he felt an idea was in line with his thoughts on clear reasoning he was glad to borrow it. He saw reason the foundation and guide in the pursuit of truth, and he was relentless in his search for absolute certainty.

Descartes is considered a revolutionary figure, especially for his attempts to change the relationship between philosophy and theology, and integrate philosophy with the new forms of science. He is respected for his attempts to create a form of philosophical argument akin to science or mathematics, his emphasis on perspective of consciousness in epistemology, and his work on methodology. Descartes has been influential to philosophers throughout the 17th and 17th centuries.

2. 1. Metaphysical Significance of Descartes' Philosophy

Rene Descartes, often called the father of modern philosophy, attempted to break with the philosophical traditions of his day and start philosophy anew. Rejecting the Aristotelian philosophy of the schools, the authority of the tradition and authority of the senses, he built a philosophical system. Descartes' started with doubt in building his metaphysical system. According to him, perceptual knowledge is uncertain and unreliable. We are deceived by our senses. Sometime, everything which can be seen by our eyes may not be true. And all things which surround us may turn out to be unreal, although our experience.

Descartes doubted everything which is known by experience. But he found that he cannot doubt the fact that he doubted. To doubt means to think and the one who was thinking must necessarily exist. Thus, it is in virtue of its power to think that the self is seen to exist and he arrived at the indubitable proposition: "I think, therefore, I am" (*Cogito ergo sum*). This proposition is said to be absolutely certain. It is clear and distinct. Its certainty inheres in its clarity and distinctness. This proposition is basic and first principle of Descartes' system of philosophy.

The rationalism of the most famous of the rationalists is problematic on two counts. First, Descartes is known as the father of modern philosophy precisely because he initiated the so called epistemological turn that is with a still. Since Descartes, philosophy has been especially concerned with the theory of knowledge, it affects others areas of philosophy. Ethics, for example, has often been, concerned with how the good might know rather than with what the good might be. With his fundamental objective of achieving certainty for his ballets,

Descartes has thus been principally responsible for the incomplete characterization of rationalism as not just etymologically but essentially connected to the claims of reason. While Descartes certainly sought to justify the claims of reason and relied upon them, even for him there are corresponding ontological views that are not less important to his system.

This second problematic aspect of Descartes' rationalism is most difficult to resolve. He holds that actually necessary truth depends on God's unconstrained will, such that even propositions that are logically contradictory might simultaneously be true. Reason itself thus seems no larger reliable and experience would seem to be the only way of determining which of the worlds even beyond logic such a powerful and unconstrained God has created. Not many of the rationalists, even among the Cartesians, followed Descartes in this radical voluntarism, and some in recent times have seen the view as ultimately incoherent. Even so, Descartes seems to have taken the view as the basic at least of his physics and perhaps of his whole system.

In Descartes' view, the universe was created by God on whose power everything depends. He thought God as resembling the human mind in that both the mind and God think, but have no physical being. But he believed that God. Unlike the human mind is that God is infinite and does not depend on a creator for his existence.

Descartes built his metaphysical system by using mathematic method. According to him, the senses are deceivers sometimes. Yet there are many things which we cannot doubt although they are known to us by our senses. So Descartes reasons logically that if there is doubt there must be a doubter. Here doubting means thinking. In this way, Descartes reaches a self-evident proposition said that nothing in the world is certain. That is I doubt or I am doubting. In this way, Descartes reaches a self-evident proposition *Cogito ergo sum* "I think therefore I am."

Descartes says that it is the first and most certain knowledge. It is the starting point for his metaphysics. It is a criterion or the test of truth. It is clear and distinct. According to Descartes, there are many ideas, which are inherent in the mind. They are innate or apriori. Among them one of the innate ideas is the ideas is the idea of God. In this way, Descartes proved himself and God.

According to Descartes mind is diametrically opposed to body. The attribute of mind is thinking. He said that mind is active and it is also free. But body (matter) is distinct from mind. The attribute of body is extension. Moreover bodies are passive. Descartes also described the relation of mind and body.

2. 2. Descartes' Method

Descartes believed in the necessity of making a new start and in establishing philosophy upon a basis of certainty, which could never be doubted. He doubted and criticized all sources of knowledge, reason, senses and authority of great men. So philosophy, for him, begins with doubt, and the attempts to get certain knowledge by systematic doubting. Mathematics contains certainty and clearness which he wanted, and he has to follow the method of mathematics. In mathematics, we begin with axioms or principles which are self-evident; next, we deduce other propositions from these axioms in such a manner that the propositions deduced are also certain. Mathematical Knowledge is a body of propositions, which are coherent and consistent with one another. And the basic and fundamental propositions, from which other propositions follow logically and deductively, are self-evident truths. Thus we have to look for such self-evident truths, or clear and distinct ideas in philosophy, in order to achieve its certainty. On the basis of the clear and distinct ideas will philosophy be able to establish certainty. Hence Descartes made his attempt by doubting

everything also to reach these clear and distinct ideas which he cannot doubt any more. Accordingly, we must strip completely of all the notions or all that we had formerly believed and we have to start denote, with intention of admitting only that which is absolutely certain. His method consists of four steps or four rules. (1) Never accept anything as true except that which was so clear and distinct as to exclude all doubt's. (2) Analyze all ideas as far as possible. (3) Arrange all ideas in what he called the order of simplicity, that is, from simple to complex. (4) Make careful and, as far as possible, complete enumeration and review of ideas thus obtained in order to be sure of having omitted nothing.

According to the rules of Descartes' method, the proper – order in philosophy is to start from the most simple and clear truths, containing the most simple notions, and then to advance step by step towards more complex truths, making sure that each step cannot be argued. And nothing can be accepted if it allows even the possibility of doubt. Only those beliefs, which are so clear and distinct that they cannot be doubted, are admitted as the basic propositions from which the remainder of all trustworthy knowledge has to be established by deductive procedure. Thus intuition and deduction are two main steps of Descartes' method.

2. 3. Descartes' Problem

Descartes' problem is to construct philosophy on a secure and profound basis so that certainty may be established in philosophy. The study of scholastic philosophy made him a skeptic, for he encountered with many problems and disputes for which no agreement may be reached among the philosophers. Thus nothing seems trustworthy to him and he recognized that he is deeply insecure. Moreover, logic and mathematics, in spite of their certainty and clearness, cannot help to know reality. Hence the only problem for Descartes, as a philosopher, is to show it is possible to construct a completely certain philosophy which cannot be doubted.

But he finds himself totally over whelmed by doubt. So the only way to solve his problem is to start with 'doubt', the only thing he possesses, since he has rejected the presumptive evidence of the senses, the reliability of the thought process and traditional knowledge.

Descartes is not only a philosopher but also a physicist and he believes that everything in nature can be explained mechanically. With regard to religion he affirms the separation of philosophy from theology. Because God is omnipotent, inaccessible and higher than all reason; man with his reason has nothing to do with this matter. So Descartes attempts to relate these three things man, God and nature in his philosophy.

2. 4. Descartes' System of Philosophy

Descartes started with doubt in building his metaphysical system. According to him perceptual knowledge is uncertain and unreliable, for we are deceived by our senses sometimes; Everything which can be seen by our eyes may not be true. And all things which surround us may turn out to be unreal, although they seem to be real through our experience. For instance, we dream and in our dreams we think that we have realities; actually they are nothing but illusions. Hence, Descartes doubted everything which is known by experience. But he found that cannot doubt the fact that he was doubting. To doubt means to think and the one who was thinking must necessarily exist. Thus, it is in virtue of its power to think, that the self is seen to exist and he arrived at the indubitable proposition, I think 'therefore, I am' (Cogito ergo sum). This proposition is said to be absolutely certain for it is clear and distinct: its certainty inheres in its clarity and distinctness. Its opposite cannot be true at all, since it is self-contradictory to think that one is not thinking. This proposition is basic and first principle of Descartes' system of philosophy. So far, Descartes demonstrated the existence of the self, or the substance.

Then he continued to prove the existence of God. God was necessary for Descartes in order that the existence of the external world may be certain. Descartes said that he found the idea of perfect God in his mind clearly and distinct the mind. God is perfect, infinite, omniscient omnipotent; on the other hand, man is imperfect and finite. Moreover, according to him, whatever exists must have a cause for existing; the cause must be as great as the effect. Hence, the idea of perfect God cannot be an idea which is invented by men who is only an imperfect being. So, God, as the cause of itself, must really exist.

Descartes also believed that God created everything, both material and immaterial things; and that the existence of the external world can be known by the account of God Himself. If the external world did not exist really, then God the creation would be a deceiver. But God, being a perfect, omnipotent substance, cannot be a deceiver at all. Hence Descartes concluded that the external world really exists. Such is the way in which Descartes furnishes his metaphysics, or his system of philosophy, by using his method of doubt.

2. 5. The Relation of Mind and Body

Descartes held that mind and body are two finite substances depending on God, the infinite substance. Both are created by God, but they are totally different from one another. Each has its own attribute. Attribute refers to the essential properties or qualities of the substance, and it necessarily or qualities of the substance and it necessarily inherein the substance and without the attribute, the substance cannot conceivably exist. Moreover, the attribute can manifest itself in different ways of modes, but modes cannot be conceived without substance and attribute while substance and attribute can be conceived without modes. For instance, figure cannot be conceived without extension, although extension can be conceived without figure, the substance cannot changes its attribute, but it can change its modes. Thus a body will always be extended, but its figure need not remain the same.

Further, attributes, are qualities which we perceive clearly and distinctly. According to this criterion, Descartes accepted extension as the attribute of body, and other qualities like sound, color, taste, smell, heat and cold are not attributes of body, because they are confused. The essence of matter consequently, is extension. Extension is a spatial continuum of three dimensions, length, breadth, and thickness, and everybody is a limited spatial magnitude. There is no such thing as empty space or vacuum, for whatever there is space there is body, Besides, space is infinite and it is infinitely divisible; there in so ultimate parts of space. Hence there are no atoms and the smallest parts of space are only corpuscles.

So far, Descartes identified matter with extension and he was led to regard it as passive. Body is conceived as more extension is passive and cannot move itself. But all variation of matter depends on motion that is the action by which a body passed from one place of another, and it is mode of the movable thing, not of a substance. Hence, it is necessary for Descartes to give a new conception of motion so that the physical world can be explained in terms of mechanics. Then he asserted that motion was communicated to matter by God from the beginning and it is always constant. The physical magnitude for motion in Descartes' philosophy is known as 'momentum or quality of motion' in science.

Hence, bodies, being identified with extension, cannot of themselves initiate or stop motion. They can neither increase nor decrease the amount of motion in the physical universe. The quantity of motion and rest must remain the same. What a body loses in motion it gives to another and the sum of motion in nature is always the same. All changes in the world of bodies must follow constant rules, or laws of nature, i.e., laws of motion. Now all the processes of the external world or the entire natural world can be explained mechanically on the bases of matter

and motion. In other words, the world, after being created by God, could develop in purely mechanical manner.

But Descartes is left with the Dualistic conception of the world consisting of two completely different realms, mind and matter. As regard their essence, mind is conscious and matter is extended. Thus all that can be experienced is a species either or spatial or of conscious being. Spatiality or the quality of filling space, and consciousness are the ultimate, simple, original attributes of reality. What is spatial is not conscious and what is conscious is not spatial. The self-certainty of mind is only that of the personality as a conscious being. Bodies are real in so far as they have in themselves the qualitative determinations of spatial existence and change, of extension and motion. All things are either bodies or minds; substances are either spatial or conscious. Hence the best problem for Descartes is to explain how these two entirely different thing, mind and matter, or mind and body are related to one another.

Conclusion

As mentioned above, Descartes assumed that the notion of reason is most important concept for the known in his philosophical view. This concept is necessary for the improvement of every society. In this paper will present that to have better understanding of the term reason. But everyone needs to understand not only reason but also experience for the improvement of human society and daily life.

Descartes' philosophy begins with doubt and ends the dualistic conception of reality, mind and matter. He brought to completion the dualism of mind and matter which began with Plato and was developed by Christian Philosophy. According to Descartes there are three determinate things namely God, mind and matter mind and matter dependent on God. The essence of the mind is thought and the essence of matter is extension.

Descartes tried to achieve his metaphysical system, using the method of mathematical reasoning in order to bring certainty and rigor in philosophy. But he uses of sorts of scholastic maxims without giving any reason. Moreover, by substance it is meant for, that which stands by itself without depending on any other thing. But Descartes took mind anybody to substance. The relation between these two, mind and body, was not clearly described also. He maintained that mind and body are so different from one another that interaction between them is not possible. Descartes thought that there is interaction between mind and body that it is the pineal gland where these two can influence on one another. Thus he could not give a consistent explanation between physical world and mental world, and the interaction between mind and body were not solved clearly in Descartes' philosophy.

It is also a weak point of Descartes that he ignored the role of experience and that he took only reasoned knowledge to be true knowledge. He also regarded mathematics as the model of clear and certain knowledge which advances step by step from one indisputable conclusion to proposition. So he used the deductive method of Geometry to establish knowledge assuming that intuitive knowledge can be achieved by using the propositions of Geometry. But some empiricists argued that truth cannot be obtained by intuitive knowledge and that intuitive knowledge is not a knowledge which is absolutely true. Thus the empiricists insisted that truth cannot be discovered by reason knowledge or by intuitive knowledge or by pointed out that the axiom of Geometry self-evident truths as Descartes thought, and they constructed a New Geometry on the basic of the axiom which is contrary to the axiom that on two parallel lines can meet so far as they are equal.

Descartes philosophy is inconsistencies. Descartes attempted to discover such truths which always hold and do not change. However, there are relative truths in human life and both relative and absolute truths are of equal importance. Descartes method is the most important in his philosophical view. It is very useful in human society and human life.

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